

Clim4**it**is

Clim4Vitis Days

09-12 July 2019

UNIFI, Florence

Italy

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 810176. This document reflects only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Clim4vitis
Climate change impact mitigation
for European viticulture

CLIM4VITIS DAYS

09-12 July 2019
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CLIM4VITIS INTRODUCTION

Clim4Vitis is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project, funded by the European Commission under the Twinning Instrument of the Horizon 2020 Programme. The project aims to promote knowledge transfer and science and technology (S&T) capacity building in viticulture and climate change. Clim4Vitis will devise new methods and tools for modelling grapevines, and for assessing climate change impacts on European viticulture.

CLIM4VITIS STAFF EXCHANGE

The staff exchange event will provide an effective knowledge transfer among Clim4Vitis partners. The speakers will address viticulture topics from different points of view, providing a general focus on the state of art and current research activities in this sector. This event is expected to promote exchanges of methodologies and best practices among partners. The event language will be English.

Target audience: researchers from partner institutions, UNIFI researchers, teaching and research staff, MSc and PhD students.

CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACTS WORKSHOP

CLIM4VITIS STAFF EXCHANGE

CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACTS WORKSHOP

This workshop will focus on the methodologies used for assessing climate change impacts in the viticulture sector. The keynote speakers will provide an overview on the current methods used for evaluating the impacts of climate change on grapevine behaviour. After each presentation, the audience will be engaged on the topics presented. A final round table will address the main findings discussed during the workshop.

The workshop will have EN-IT/IT-EN simultaneous translation.

Target audience: researchers from partner institutions, agronomist and stakeholders from the winemaking sector, MSc and PhD students.

For Credits

The participation in the 2-days Workshop and Staff exchange will award:

- Agronomists and technicians with 0,5 CFP/workshop/day and 0,5 CFP/staff exchange.

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clim4vitis.eu/event/clim4vitisdays-2/

More info:
www.clim4vitis.eu
www.researchgate.net/project/Clim4Vitis-H2020-Twinning
 Luisa Leolini | clim4vitis.florence@gmail.com

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AGENDA

09 JULY

Sala Comparetti
Piazza Brunelleschi, 4, Florence

CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACTS WORKSHOP

10 JULY

Sala Comparetti
Piazza Brunelleschi, 4, Florence

12 JULY

Aula Magna Scuola di Agraria
Piazzale delle Cascine, 18, Florence

CLIM4VITIS STAFF EXCHANGE

14:30 - 14:40	Registration
14:40 - 14:45	Welcome Marco Bindi - UNIFI, Florence, Italy
14:45 - 15:15	CLIM4Vitis project presentation Jose A. Santos - UTAD, Vila Real, Portugal
15:15 - 16:00	Impact of climate change on crops: possible approaches Marco Moriondo - CNR-IBIMET, Florence, Italy
16:00 - 16:15	Coffee Break
16:15 - 17:00	Integrated methodologies for assessing the impacts of climate change on multifaceted-aspects of crops production via the spatial application of process-based models Giovanni Cappelli - CREA, Bologna, Italy
17:00 - 17:45	Precision Wine, a geographical decision support system for viticulture developed in Italy and France Vittorio Marletto - ARPAE, Bologna, Italy
17:45 - 18:00	Wrap up and final comments Marco Bindi - UNIFI, Florence, Italy
09:00 - 09:05	Registration
09:05 - 09:15	Opening Marco Bindi - UNIFI, Florence, Italy
09:15 - 10:00	Climate change and viticultural sector Antonello Bonfante - CNR-ISAFO, Naples, Italy
10:00 - 10:45	Phytopathological models and Decision Support Systems for the Integrated pest management of vine Federico Spanna - Regione Piemonte, Turin, Italy
	The crop model IVINE as an Instrument to monitor physiological and phenological vineyard conditions Claudio Cassardo - UNITO, Turin, Italy
10:45 - 11:00	Coffee Break
11:00 - 11:45	Research in Viticulture Giovanni Battista Mattioli & Linda Salvi - UNIFI, Florence, Italy
11:45 - 12:20	Open debate Aureliano Malheiro - UTAD, Vila Real, Portugal
12:20 - 12:30	Wrap up and final comments Marco Bindi - UNIFI, Florence, Italy
12:30 - 13:30	Light lunch
09:00 - 09:10	Registration
09:10 - 09:15	Welcome Marco Moriondo - CNR-IBIMET, Florence, Italy
09:15 - 09:45	Role of cover crops for vineyards in Mediterranean environment Giovanni Argenti - UNIFI, Florence, Italy
09:45 - 10:15	Insect pests in Tuscan vineyards under climate changes Patrizia Sacchetti - UNIFI, Florence, Italy
10:15 - 10:45	The Influence of climate on wine quality Anna Dalla Marta - UNIFI, Florence, Italy
10:45 - 11:00	Coffee Break
11:00 - 11:30	Precision Agriculture: effective technological development for Sustainable Precision Agriculture requires ecosystem supports Marco Vieri - UNIFI, Florence, Italy
11:30 - 12:00	Climate change Impacts and adaptation measures for the Portuguese viticulture: a modelling approach Helder Fraga - UTAD, Vila Real, Portugal
12:00 - 12:30	Rural "products" and consumer behaviour: text analysis and neuro sensing for the evaluation of the consumer's preferences in the wine sector Sara Fabbri & Irene Capecci - UNIFI, Florence, Italy
12:30 - 13:00	Closing session Marco Moriondo - CNR-IBIMET, Florence, Italy
13:00	Light lunch

WORKSHOP

09-10 July 2019

Sala Comparetti, Florence

Italy

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Climate change impact mitigation for European viticulture: knowledge transfer for an integrated approach

Clim4Vitis is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project, funded by the European Commission under the Twinning instrument of the Horizon 2020 Programme. The prime objective of Clim4Vitis is to strengthen capacity and performance in two main specific fields of research in viticulture & climate: (1) Grapevine modelling; and (2) Methods and tools for assessing climate change impacts on European viticulture, in general, and on grapevine productivity, quality attributes and risk of diseases and pests in particular. The consortium comprises the following partners: Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro (UTAD) – coordinator; Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK); Università degli studi di Firenze (UNIFI); Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST); and Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação (SPI).

The Clim4Vitis Launch Event aims to disseminate the project among researchers, stakeholders and the general public interested in the topic of viticulture & climate. Prominent invited speakers, from both the academy and the winemaking sector, coming from different European countries, will provide state-of-the-art information on this very pertinent topic, particularly under the current context of changing climates. The threats, challenges and opportunities of climate change to European vitiviculture will be unveiled by their exciting and complementary communications.

For more information please visit the Clim4Vitis project website on <https://clim4vitis.eu/>

Thank you very much for coming and enjoy!

The Clim4Vitis team

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Impact of climate change on crops: possible approaches

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ABSTRACT

Two main approaches have been generally applied to predict the impact of climate change on crop distribution in the next future: statistical models and process based approaches. The first approach assumes that the spatial distribution of a crop is mainly determined by environmental conditions and that this distribution has reached equilibrium with these factors. Building on these premises, a cultivation is confined to a climatic niche that is characterised by different bio-climatic factors and climatic change may alter this equilibrium leading to changes in potential cultivated area of a crop. These assumptions make this approach particularly appealing to outline possible changes in cultivation of a crop on a large scale since many climatic and environmental data are available at high spatial resolution required for these assessments. In crop process based models, crop behaviour is defined by a range of relationships describing the main plant processes such as crop phenology, photosynthesis and biomass accumulation and therefore may be a tool to address the issue on climate change effect on crop yield and to outline where a certain crop would be profitable or not in the next future. To provide reliable results, the use of this approach requires in many cases the use of many input variables at high spatial and temporal resolution, such as environmental data (daily meteorological data, soil texture and depth) and management practices (fertilisation). As such, these needs make the approach not readily applicable especially on national or continental scale where these data are difficultly available on the required resolution.

Integrated methodologies for assessing the impacts of climate change on multifaceted-aspects of crops production via the spatial application of process-based models

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ABSTRACT

Crop models mathematically represent dynamic interactions between plant, weather, soil and farming practices. They have been increasingly applied, from field to regional and global scale applications, to understand and quantify the trade-off between productivity, management and the sustainability of cropping systems, in terms of responsible use of resources (e.g. water and nitrogen) and of adaptation to or mitigation of climate change impacts.

This contribution focuses on the most recent information about the quantification of climate change impact on crop productions via the spatially-explicit application of process-based models, providing an overview of major assumptions and criticalities related to this methodological approach and of potential applications in the viticulture sector. In this context, cropping systems will be analysed considering impact of alternative farming practices on a variety of yield-limiting factors, related to water availability, disease pressure, air pollution (i.e. ozone concentration) and fruit quality.

The core of models applications herein presented is BioMA (Biophysical Model Applications; <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/BioMA>), which is a platform to run biophysical models on generic spatial units, currently in use at the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission for yield forecasting. Within this framework, the cropping system is divided into different domain-specific compartments (e.g. crop, soil, agro-management practices,...), which are coded, separately, in independent software units named components. Model components can be then inter-connected into more complex simulation chains customized for specific modelling goals (modelling solutions) and coupled with spatially explicit database with information on climate, crop

distribution, and soil properties. This allows to represent the biophysical interactions between the crop and its environment by handling the interactions between the I/O data produced by the different components and further foster reuse, scalability, incremental improvement and maintenance of modelling approaches, opening them to contribution from sub-domain specialists.

Precision Wine: a geographical decision support system for viticulture developed in Italy and France

Marletto, Vittorio¹, Antolini, Gabriele¹, Volta, Antonio¹, Tomei, Fausto¹, Villani, Giulia¹, Bois, Benjamin², Campagnolo Stefano³

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³ GAIAG srl, via Aurelio Saffi, 34, 47521 Cesena, Italy

ABSTRACT

The main features of a geographical Decision Support System for precision viticulture are presented, together with results obtained in two pilot sites (Italy and France). The PW DSS makes use of real time weather data monitoring, digital terrain models, soil and cultivar parameters, remote sensing, crop soil and disease modelling, geographical information systems, and is particularly suited for wine growers consortia.

Products available from PW can be grouped in the following categories: weather data and forecasts, interpolated micrometeorological maps, soil conditions (moisture and temperature profiles), vine status variables (phenology, leaf area, grape growth), disease risk (powdery and downy mildew), system configuration and management tools. PW provides vineyard operation advice including irrigation timing and amounts, and forecasts final harvest date, together with quantity and quality of grapes.

The development of the Precision Wine DSS was supported by the European Community in the framework of the EUFP7 Vintage project (2011-2015, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/101471/en>). From year 2015 the system entered its operational phase, managed by Gaiag srl, a small Italian company charged with running the system and expanding its market uptake.

Climate change and viticultural sector

Bonfante, Antonello¹

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ABSTRACT

Climate change (CC) directly influences agricultural sectors, presenting the need to identify both adaptation and mitigation actions that can make local farming communities and crop production more resilient. In this context, the viticultural sector is one of those most challenged by CC due to the need to combine grape quality, grapevine cultivar adaptation and therefore farmers' future incomes. Thus, understanding how suitability for viticulture is changing under CC is of primary interest in the development of adaptation strategies in traditional wine-growing regions.

In this context, two main procedures can be defined to face CC effects on viticultural sector, working at different spatial and temporal scale: (i) planning and (ii) management procedures.

The first procedures refer to the evaluation of the expected future climate scenarios effects on the soil-plant-climate interaction and then on plant growth and grape quality responses, in order to: (i) make decision to how adapt your production area to climate change; (ii) evaluate the potentiality of new territories to vineyard land use; (iii) evaluate the resilience of current terroir to CC.

The second addressed to the management of vineyard on current climate conditions (site specific management), which are oriented to optimize the use of resources (e.g. water, pesticides), preserving the environment health and wine quality. From this perspective, the aim of this contribution is to show the current approaches from literature, paying particular attention to the planning procedures.

Phytopathological models and Decision Support Systems for the integrated pest management of vine

Spanna, Federico¹

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ABSTRACT

Current European phytosanitary regulations require member states to set up agrometeorological operational services to support decisions in agriculture, also using modeling tools for predicting and simulating biotic or abiotic plant diseases.

In this way, many agrometeorological services are carrying on activities for the development, validation and calibration of phytopathological and entomologic models which, by using basic agro-meteorological data, provide the simulation of the development of the different phases of the biological cycle and allow the user to have a support for decision making.

In the specific case of phytosanitary defense, the knowledge and interpretation of the model's outputs allow to choose the best time for the application of phytosanitary treatments and the best product to be used.

Some of the vine the most widespread and most useful models are related to the development of diseases such as downy mildew, oidium and botrytis, while in the entomological field the phenological model referred to the development of *Lobesia botrana* is mainly used, while it is still in experimental phase the one related to the phenological development of *Scaphoideus titanus*, vector of the phytoplasma causal agent of the disease *flavescence dorée*.

These models should be accessible through informatic platforms and they should be easy to use and to be correctly interpreted by agricultural technicians and advisors in order to allow the rapid use of the related informations.

The application of these models could be expanded and enhanced through the use of numerical meteorological forecast data. In this way the outputs would allow farmers to be able to correctly plan their activities.

A further development could be the integration of these phytosanitary models with crop-growth models in order to develop a system of quantification of the productive damage.

The crop model IVINE as an instrument to monitor physiological and phenological vineyard conditions

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ABSTRACT

Crop productivity depends upon several factors related to soil properties and fertility, management practices, meteorological conditions, and climate. The latter is deserving growing attention since there is a need for a reliable assessment of the effects under a changing climate. In this respect, it is essential to primarily understand how and how much both climate and meteorology affect grape productivity and quality. Crop models are emerging as essential tools for investigating the effects of climate change on crop development and growth via the integration of existing knowledge of crop physiology and phenology.

The monitoring of physical and physiological processes related to environmental conditions influencing vine growth, yield and grape quality is associated with numerical and empirical models simulating physical, physiological, and phenological processes and diagnosing microscale plant responses to environment. These models constitute tools able to help the managing of vineyards and improve the wine quality.

The crop model IVINE (Italian Vineyard Integrated Numerical model for Estimating physiological values) has been developed to simulate physiological and phenological vineyard conditions. The model requires boundary (temperature, relative humidity, solar global radiation, PAR, soil temperature and water content, wind, rainfall, and leaf wetness) and initial (vineyard and soil characteristics, geographic informations, plant density, variety characteristics, and vineyard management) conditions. The main model outputs are: the main phenological phases timing (dormancy break, budburst, flowering, fruit-set, veraison, harvest), the leaf development, the yield, the sugar concentration, and the predawn leaf water potential. The model has been

calibrated for some cultivars (namely Nebbiolo), validated through intercomparison with observations, and also applied over a period of climatological relevance (sixty years). The results reveal that the model seems able to evaluate the most characteristic variables related to the vine. A close look on the time trend during the 60-years period reveal significant trends for many variables.

Research in Viticulture

Mattii, Giovan Battista¹, Cataldo, Eleonora¹, Paoli, Francesca¹, Salvi, Linda¹, Sbraci, Sofia¹

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ABSTRACT

LIFE Zeowine

The LIFE ZEOWINE project is a demonstration project aimed at improving soil protection and management, the plant health and the quality of production in the wine-growing sector, including organic and biodynamic productions, through the use of an innovative product resulting from the composting of wastes of the wine productive chain and Zeolites.

Starting from the proven efficacy features for both compost and zeolite, the protocols for the production of ZEOWINE and its application in fertilizer production and plant are defined to demonstrate that its adoption in viticulture improves soil properties and the physiological characteristics of the plant. The synergism of the positive effects on the soil and the plant will consequently be reflected in the improvement of the characteristics of the grapes and the wines

Uva Pretiosa

The general objective of the strategic plan is to carry out valorization processes for the main by-products and waste from the wine-making chain, turning them into products with high added value and reducing final waste to the maximum, in a circular economy perspective. These operations will be implemented through the introduction of innovative technologies and processing techniques, gathering as many useful elements as possible to define economic and environmental sustainability. In particular, the transfer of innovation will be addressed for the enhancement of the following by-products: immature grapes, grape marc, pomace and grape seeds.

Irrigation

The objective of the project is to develop a strategy that includes the use of irrigation in viticulture to improve the quality of production on two different cultivars, Sauvignon blanc and Merlot. The production goals are extremely different, as in the first cultivar the goal is to

preserve the fruity and vegetable aromas as much as possible, while in the second it is to increase the polyphenolic and antioxidant content.

STAFF EXCHANGE

12 July 2019

Aula Magna – Scuola di Agraria, Florence

Italy

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Role of cover crops for vineyards in Mediterranean environment

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ABSTRACT

In last decades, an alternative management to conventional tillage of soil in vineyards was represented by cover cropping. Advantages are mainly related to erosion control, improvement of soil aggregation, water infiltration, increase in organic matter content, fertility and soil microbial activity. In addition to improved provision of ecosystem services, including cultural services, cover crops may facilitate mechanization management and efficiency of vineyard operations, useful to environmental sustainability. Despite these benefits, competition for water can lead to relevant stress with impacts on growth of vines, grape yields and wine quality, especially in areas with reduced summer rainfall. To enhance positive effects of cover cropping is therefore essential a proper choice of vegetal material to be sown, with special reference to peculiar Mediterranean environmental features, such as pedological and climatic conditions. For these reasons a great number of researches were devoted to analyse the effects of different species (sometimes in mixtures) in comparison to conventional tillage or spontaneous species naturally developing on the ground. In many Mediterranean environments important results were obtained by using self-reseeding legumes, mainly represented by subterranean clovers (*Trifolium subterraneum*, *T. brachycalycinum*) or annual medics (*Medicago* species): their importance is due primarily to the peculiar vegetative rhythm which is asynchronous to that of the grapevine, reducing in this way water competition. A major issue is anyway the management of the artificial sward as cover crops can explicate their potentiality only if proper utilised. Moreover, in particular agricultural systems, as organic or biodynamic farming, cover cropping can be performed by green manure, and in this case objectives can be also represented by nutrient fertilisation, adopting monocultures or mixtures, including not only legumes but also grasses or cruciferous plants. In this context, management techniques, in terms of time of harvest and C/N ratio, are the main

factors for ensuring an efficient utilization of the sown crop and managing insects, diseases and weeds.

Insect pests in Tuscan vineyards under climate changes

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ABSTRACT

Insects are poikilothermic animals with growth and development greatly affected by environmental temperature. Moreover, other abiotic factors such as relative humidity, precipitation and wind, among meteorological variables, can positively or negatively impact insect population dynamics.

Besides, insect pests feeding on plants are indirectly influenced by climate since this favors or prevents the phenology, growth and availability of host plants. It's known that grapevines and viticulture are highly sensitive to climate changes, as a consequence, grapevine insect pests can be greatly impacted by long term temperature variations. Moreover, the response of insect pests in viticulture can be modulated by their relationships with the crop also in terms of territorial distribution, lower and upper thermal thresholds of development, adaptability to new situations.

Investigations on life history modifications and development models have been carried out mainly on the European grapevine moth, *Lobesia botrana*, showing a faster growth of the insect in this new scenario.

On the basis of published literature, personal observations and current researches, a summary of the main insect pests attacking wine grapes in Tuscany during the last two decades is outlined. Among insect pests of vineyards, multivoltine species belonging to Hemiptera order that possibly have been affected by climate changes are leafhoppers, grape phylloxera and mealybugs. Climatic variables more significant for the development of these insect pests are highlighted and evidences of the impact of climate changes on features of their life cycles are discussed. Current researches

on grape phylloxera aimed at studying the recent recurrence in different areas of Tuscany are described and debated in the light of the ongoing climate changes.

The influence of climate on wine quality

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³ *LaMMA Consortium, Florence, Italy*

ABSTRACT

The quality of wine depends on several factors including soil, agronomic management, grape variety and climate conditions. Among them, climate is the most variable factor being subjected to natural year to year variations and to an increased variability, especially related to extreme events occurrence, as a result of climate change.

In particular, temperature and rainfall trends during the active period of grapevine in Mediterranean area, from late dormancy to harvest period, strongly affect the final quality of grape. The positive and adverse impacts of climate on wine production mainly depends on the scale of occurrence.

On one hand, local and micrometeorological conditions drive the main biophysical processes concurring to final yield and its quality, included the development of pests and diseases as well as the occurrence of other abiotic stresses. On the other hand, the impact of atmospheric climate patterns (large-scale) seems to be larger than the local scale variability, as demonstrate by a general improvement of wine quality due to warmer and drier climate conditions occurring in the last decades. In this sense, large scale climate features, which are relatively more persistent and therefore more predictable, show a good forecasting potential.

In this work, an analysis of the role of local, regional and large-scale climate conditions on the determination of wine quality in the Mediterranean area, based on case studies, is presented.

Precision Agriculture: effective technological development for Sustainable Precision Agriculture requires ecosystem supports

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ABSTRACT

Over these last three decades the evolution in farming available technologies offers new possibilities to measure and to control environmental, biological, technical and entrepreneurial resources.

Farming activities can now avail of a huge universe of technologies to better manage practices with the aim of adding values and reduce wastes. Sustainability is a constraint not only to ensure revenue for farmers, but to act best practices in accordance with soil and environment conservation and now in the effort to mitigate climate change effects.

Innovation in agriculture has different approach in closed environment (greenhouses, livestock, nursery, agrofood factories) and on open field (as to say farming)). In farming seasonability, changeability in soil and weather condition, timeliness, all occur to make extremely complex and variable the management system. Different tools as sensors, in synergy with predictive models and decision support systems are needed to appropriately control the right practices to be actuated. Mechatronics and automation get it possible to act more precise and faster operations. Telemetry and now IoT make farming operations and products traceable.

Digital traceability and connectivity makes it possible to monitor the single steps of the very variable operations to apply lean control.

This technological system makes it possible and enhance managerial procedure introducing lean farming and climate and quality control by the Farm Management Integrated Systems.

This new complex system needs a multi-actors and multi-competencies that may provide an appropriate holistic supports in the educational system to train human resources, the consultants, the providers, the assistant services companies for HD and SW, the specific governance.

We tested some living experiences in regional Operative Group projects aimed to the developing, PA techniques, PA practices and a territorial digital platform for grape, grain and oil olive producers.

Climate change impacts and adaptation measures for the Portuguese viticulture: a modelling approach

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ABSTRACT

Climate is one of the most important factors determining grapevine yields and grape quality. The assessment of climate change impacts on this crop is crucial for the sustainability of this important socio-economic sector. In the present study, the impacts of climate change on Portuguese viticulture are analysed by coupling the crop model STICS with high resolution climatic simulations, for both recent-past (1981-2005) and future (2041-2070, under RCP8.5) periods. Daily gridded climatic variables, soil properties and terrain characteristics over Portugal are determined and used as STICS inputs. The results highlight yield decreases in the innermost winemaking regions, mostly in Alentejo and Douro. For these regions, extreme temperatures and severe dryness are expected to cause negative impacts on yields and quality attributes. As a strategy against these impacts, adaptation measures are considered as a modelling exercise, focusing at specific problems. Particularly, the use of deficit irrigation and mulching application are simulated within STICS. Results show that irrigation and mulching may mitigate the negative impacts of the projected warming and drying, up to a certain extent. As such, other adaptation strategies must be considered, such as changes in management practices or in oenological practices, and/or long term adaptation measures, such as vineyard relocation and variety-clone-rootstock selection. Adequate and timely planning of these measures need to be adopted by the winemaking sector, as the readiness to define and implement adaptation strategies to climate change will result in lower detrimental impacts.

Rural "products" and consumer behaviour: text analysis and neuro sensing for the evaluation of the consumer's preferences in the wine sector

Barbierato, Elena¹, Bernetti, Iacopo¹, Capecchi, Irene¹, Cipollaro, Maria¹, Fabbrizzi, Sara¹, Menghini, Silvio¹, Sacchelli, Sandro¹

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ABSTRACT

The emotional answer to a visual stimulus and its verbalization improve the knowledge of consumer's behaviour, providing a useful informative support for the implementation of both marketing strategies and public policy. This work deals with two different methodological approaches: the text analysis and the neuro sensing.

Text analysis

Text analysis techniques explore extended and/or not structured textual corpora. The reported examples are connected both to the quantitative analysis of the scientific literature and to the semantic analysis of the web textual material. This method has been applied to the scientific literature regarding sustainability, climate change impacts and adaptation strategies on wine sector. Semantic analysis has concerned tags analysis of Big data extracted from the Flickr Network. The analysis of 9304 tags regarding the rural landscape of Chianti Classico area has highlighted how people perceive landscape and it provides some interesting starting points for landscape monitoring and management. This method could be a step toward the consideration of public perception and the connection between the semantics to the expert-based spatial data collected for landscape evaluation.

Neuro sensing

The winery is the catalyst of wine consumption and purchase choices. It's important to know how and how much the servicescape, particularly spatial layout, gives a positive touristic experience and influences the consumers' behaviour. Application of neuro sensing method, that uses new technologies as virtual reality, eye-tracking and electroencephalogram, allows to understand the

emotions caused by the environment of cellar doors. While the interviewees live a 3D experience of the cellar door, the eye movement, through Pupil Lab platform, and the brain activity, through Muse platform are scanned and recorded. The monitoring of brain activities allows to understand the emotion felt by the interviewees. The eye tracking allows to link this emotion with the elements observed, in order to elaborate marketing strategies.

Clim4^uitis